

Super-resolution for terrain modeling using deep learning in High Mountain Asia

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Abstract—High Mountain Asia (HMA) has the most complex and rugged terrain in the world. However, the high-resolution terrain data in HMA is not easy to acquire. A modified super-resolution residual network in the study is trained, in order to develop super-resolution DEMs in the HMA. Limited high resolution (HR) DEMs from other areas and freely available DEM data from the HMA is used to train the model. We constructed a new loss function which constrains the network learning and convergence by using the terrain parameters of slope and curvature. A comparative analysis between the proposed method and existing methods was conducted. The results demonstrate that MSRResNet can achieve highly accurate terrain data in the process of downscaling DEMs in HMA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Terrain is a key component in the processes that occur at the landscape ^[1]. The High Mountain Asia (HMA) area should be given more attention, which is characterized by some of the most complex and highest terrain conditions in the world. Digital elevation models (DEMs) are widely used to represent terrain ^[2]. In HMA areas, the popular DEMs used is usually global free access elevation data, such as ASTER GDEM, SRTM ^[3-4], which are freely available with a resolution of 1 arc-second. However, higher resolution DEMs are still needed in this area, and many earth science studies require finer scale elevation data ^[5-6].

Deep learning (DL)-based methods have also been proposed for the development of super-resolution DEMs from existing elevation data. These studies transferred the frameworks of EDSR ^[7], SRGAN ^[8] and ESRCAN ^[9] from images to DEMs and then obtain the super-resolution DEMs. However, the DL methods mostly ignore terrain knowledge in the process of super-resolution. Terrain parameters are usually used to express terrain characteristics ^[10], and they can be divided into types, i.e., first- and second-order terrain parameters. Thus, the integration of DL

and terrain parameters is promising for improving the accuracy of generated HR DEMs.

In this paper, a modified super-resolution residual network (MSRResNet) is trained to generate super-resolution DEMs in HMA areas. It uses freely available DEMs from HMA and limited HR DEMs from other regions. A new loss function is constructed by considering the first-order and second-order terrain parameters in this network. We also compare the accuracies between the proposed method and existing super-resolution methods (i.e., the SRGAN deep learning method and the Bicubic spatial interpolation method) to assess the effectiveness of MSRResNet.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

HMA, which is a high-altitude mountain region in Central Asia ^[11-12], is selected as the study area. The Hengduan Mountains, having treacherous topography conditions in the southeastern HMA, is the test area. The huge differences in elevation of the Hengduan Mountains between river valleys and ridges make it one of the most complex areas of the HMA. The test area and study area are shown in Fig. 1. The detailed information of the experimental data is shown in Table 1. The scale factor is 8 for the super-resolution experiment, which means the experimental results in resolution achieve an eight-fold improvement.

B. Methods

The Flowchart of the DEM super-resolution framework in HMA is shown in Fig. 2. The loss function mainly consists of basic GAN loss, elevation loss, slope loss, curvature loss, and perceptual loss. Among them, elevation loss is the most common

loss, and is pixel-based. Slope and curvature are commonly terrain parameters [13], and we transform the two parameters into MSRResNet losses. In addition, perceptual loss has the advantages in extracting high level detailed terrain knowledge. We added perceptual loss to help the network extract overall terrain knowledge.

III. RESULTS

(1) Elevation

As shown in Table 2, MSRResNet outperforms the other methods in MAE, RMSE, PSNR, and SSIM from 120 m to 15 m. MSRResNet improves RMSE accuracy by 32.17% and MAE accuracy by 33.97% compared with Bicubic. And it improves RMSE accuracy by 39.15% and MAE accuracy by 32.47% compared to SRGAN. Fig. 3 shows the DEMs produced by different methods. The results show that MSRResNet network

achieves more detailed terrain features. And SRGAN and Bicubic show clear smoothing effects.

(2) Slope

As shown in Fig. 4, the slope results by MSRResNet method appear close to those from the reference high resolution DEM. Many detailed terrain information can be found by our method.

(3) Stream network

We also compared the stream networks generated by several reconstructed DEMs and experimentally proved that the stream networks generated by MSRResNet is the closest to the stream networks generated by the reference DEM.

TABLE I. BASIC INFORMATION OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Data	Location	High Resolution DEM		Low Resolution DEM	
		Resolution	Data Source	Resolution	Data Source
Training Data	25° - 52.5° N, 70° - 105°E	30m	ASTER GDEM v3	240m	90m SRTM DEM
	22° - 29° N, 106° - 117°E	30m	ASTER GDEM v3	240m	90m SRTM DEM
	34° - 40° N, 106° - 111°E	5m	http://www.sxgis.cn/	40m	30m ASTER GDEM v3
Testing Data	26° - 26.5° N, 98.9° - 99.5°E	15m	ZY-3	120m	90m SRTM DEM

Figure 1. The study area in the Hengduan Mountains in HMA. The small areas represented by A, B, and C are used for evaluation.

Figure. 2. The flowchart for the DEM super resolution framework in HMA.

TABLE II. ELEVATION ERROR EVALUATION WITH DIFFERENT METHODS.

	Bicubic	SRGAN	MSRResNet
MAE (m)	25.23	24.67	16.66
RMSE (m)	30.96	34.51	21.00
PSNR (dB)	31.48	30.52	34.27
SSIM	0.9501	0.9511	0.9512
Standard deviation (m)	30.96	32.45	20.69

Figure 3. Comparison of reconstructed DEMs in areas A, B and C.

Figure 4. Surface slope by different methods in areas A, B and C.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a modified super-resolution residual network (MSRResNet) is trained to generate super-resolution DEMs in HMA areas. It uses freely available DEMs from HMA and limited HR DEMs from other regions. A new loss function is constructed by considering the first-order and second-order terrain parameters in this network. We also compare the accuracies between the proposed method and existing super-resolution methods (i.e., the SRGAN deep learning method and the Bicubic spatial interpolation method) to assess the effectiveness of MSRResNet. We can obtain 15m DEMs based on the freely available 30m DEMs in HMA region. In the future, the proposed super-resolution method can be applied to obtain corresponding HR DEMs for other inaccessible regions to advance scientific researches.

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